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The Buddhism in the Contemporary Context of Religion, Morality and Law

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Abstract: From time to time men find themselves forced to reconsider current and inherited beliefs and ideas, to gain some harmony between present and past experience, and to reach a position which shall satisfy the demands of feeling and reflection and give confidence for facing the future. If, at the present day, religion, as a subject of critical or scientific inquiry, of both practical and theoretical significance has attracted increasing attention, this can be ascribed to:

1. The rapid progress of scientific knowledge and thought;
2. The deeper intellectual interest in the subject;
3. The widespread tendencies in all parts of the world to reform or reconstruct religion, or even to replace it by some body of thought, more , rational and 'scientific' or less 'superstitious' and
4. The effect of social, political, and international events of a sort which, in the past, have both influenced and been influenced by religion.

Keywords: Buddhism and Social Work, Dhamma, Morality, Science

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